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SUSTAINABILITY OF MOLDOVAN WINEMAKING IN THE FRAMEWORK OF GLOBAL SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHANGES

Abstract: *Moldovan winemaking, with its ancient roots, faces challenges and opportunities in the context of global socio-economic changes. Environmental sustainability requires adaptation to climate change through the selection of resilient grape varieties and organic practices. Economic sustainability is achieved by diversifying export markets, developing brands, and supporting small producers. Social sustainability includes preserving cultural heritage and ensuring fair labor practices. Government support and international cooperation play a key role in creating favorable conditions for the sustainable development of the winemaking industry.*

Keywords: sustainability, winemaking, changes, globalization

Winemaking in Moldova has ancient origins, with archaeological evidence suggesting that viticulture has been practiced in the region for over 5,000 years. The favorable climate, fertile soil, and diverse grape varieties have long made Moldova a prime location for viticulture. Throughout history, Moldovan wine has been celebrated for its quality, and the industry has seen periods of prosperity and decline influenced by political and economic shifts.

Today, Moldova is one of the top wine producers in Eastern Europe, with a significant portion of its wine exported to various countries worldwide. The country boasts a wide range of grape varieties, including both local and international types, and produces a diverse array of wines, from dry reds and whites to sparkling and dessert wines. The industry is a crucial part of the Moldovan economy, providing employment and contributing to GDP.

One of the most pressing challenges for the sustainability of Moldovan winemaking is climate change. Changes in temperature, precipitation patterns, and the frequency of extreme weather events can significantly affect grape growing conditions. Moldovan winemakers must adapt to these changes to maintain the quality and yield of their vineyards.

The winegrowing and winemaking complex is a strategically important sector of the Moldovan economy. Currently, the wine sector is going through a number of difficulties: total change of the main export-markets, pandemic, refugee crisis, inflation and energy crisis. Overcoming these challenges is possible through the widespread implementation of sustainable development.

Historically, Moldova has relied heavily on specific export markets, particularly Russia and other CIS countries. Recent geopolitical tensions and trade

restrictions have forced Moldovan winemakers to pivot towards new markets. This shift requires substantial investment in marketing, compliance with new regulatory standards, and building new trade relationships.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on global trade, including the wine industry. Lockdowns, supply chain disruptions, and reduced consumer spending have all contributed to a decline in wine sales. Moldovan winemakers have had to adapt by increasing their online presence, exploring direct-to-consumer sales, and finding new ways to engage with international buyers.

The ongoing regional conflicts have led to a refugee crisis, affecting labor availability and stability in rural areas where vineyards and wineries are located. This crisis has put additional strain on the local economy and resources, requiring coordinated efforts to ensure the well-being of both the local population and the refugees.

The Republic of Moldova is the country with the largest number of vines per capita. The importance of the wine sector is evident from the sector's share in the gross domestic product: 3% of GDP and 8% of total exports in 2023. There are about 215 wineries in the country, 70,000 Moldovan families own their own vineyards and produce wine, and the total number of people employed directly or indirectly in the wine sector is 200,000. Moldova is one of the few European wine-producing countries capable of producing a wide range of wines.

Evolution of wine production, mln dal

Fig.1: Evolution of wine production, mln, (Source: Stefan Iamandi, Conjunctura vitivinicolă, 2023)

From the 2023 harvest, 263 thousand tons of grapes were processed (280 thousand tons in 2022), from which 17.8 million dal of wine materials were produced. If we consider the evolution of wine production (without brandy wine materials), the figure of 12.6 million dal is below the 10-year average (13 million dal) by 11% and is equal to the volumes obtained in 2009, 2014 and 2015

In the Moldovan winegrowing and winemaking sector, the course towards sustainability was set out in the draft strategy for the development of the sector “Wine of Moldova - 2030”. In this document, it was recognized that, apart from the problem of pesticide management, the most pressing issues that need to be addressed

in terms of sustainable development are related to the management of winemaking waste.

The existing practices at domestic wineries are clearly inferior to international best practices and carry the potential to create environmental risks, hazards to human, animal and plant health, and damage to our country's reputation on the world market. This applies to wastewater, cake and other by-products.

Fig. 2: Waste recycling (Source: Stefan Iamandi, Conjunctura vitivinicolă, 2023)

The figure above shows how the waste from wine production can be recycled. For example: calcium tartrate can be produced from pomace, yeast and combs. And from the seeds, peduncle, oil and fiber. We need alcohol and tartaric acid in our production. But we throw away this waste and buy, for example, tartaric acid for 10-12 euros/kg. If we sell all the products we get, we can invest 60% of the money to build a recycling plant. It also increases our competitiveness and sustainability, because waste generation creates risks for the environment, and wineries pay for it. Sustainable development also includes economic efficiency.

Here we would like to cite the following case study. Back in 2005, wine accounted for a quarter of the country's total export earnings. Almost all of Moldova's wine was exported to Russia. The product embargo imposed by Russia against Moldova in 2006 was a disaster for the wine industry in the short term, but in the long term it served as a real incentive for the production of higher quality wine, which became in demand in other markets.

To maintain competitiveness, Moldovan winemakers are diversifying their export markets, targeting the EU, Asia, and North America. Creating a strong brand and marketing strategies are important aspects. Supporting small and medium-sized producers through cooperatives, access to financing, and investments also plays a key role.

Preserving the cultural heritage of winemaking requires education and training of new generations. Winemaking enterprises must ensure fair labor practices and contribute to the development of local communities through investments in infrastructure and participation in philanthropy.

Today Moldova chooses stable partners for export. It is worth mentioning here how the export of Moldovan products has changed, as well as how the price of 1 bottle has changed. If we evaluate the last ten years, thanks to the work done by Moldovan winemakers on quality, Moldova was able to go from wine that was sold at 38 cents per bottle to 1.70 cents. It can be noted that Moldova has grown phenomenally in a market that is occupied by countries that have established themselves in the production of quality wines.

Table: Top exporting countries and price per 1 bottle of wine in 2023

(Source: Stefan Iamandi, Conjunctura vitivinicolă, 2023)

Export Market. Top-countries	Bottled Wine. Average Price	Dynamics of the Price (%)
Romania	2.37 USD	3 ↑
Czech Republic	1.41 USD	16 ↑
Poland	1.51 USD	16 ↑
China	1.73 USD	14 ↓
Netherlands	1.69 USD	11 ↑
Canada	1.31 USD	6 ↑
Russian Federation	1.40 USD	5 ↑
Turkey	1.59 USD	3 ↑
Ukraine	1.53 USD	15 ↑
Kazakhstan	1.13 USD	5 ↓
Slovakia	1.49 USD	14 ↑
Latvia	1.36 USD	16 ↑
Serbia	1.50 USD	19 ↑
Great Britain	1.47 USD	19 ↑
USA	2.25 USD	3 ↑
Germany	1.92 USD	14 ↑
Ghana	1.61 USD	0 ↓
Lithuania	1.45 USD	13 ↑
Ivory Coast	1.69 USD	33 ↑
Japan	3.29 USD	17 ↑
Average	1.70 USD	9 ↑

Russia's aggressive war against Ukraine has aggravated the energy situation in Moldova, and with another drought reducing the productivity of the wine sector. Real GDP growth After a strong rebound of 13.9% in 2021, real GDP declined sharply by 5.0% in 2022. High inflation (28.7% on average in 2022) caused by high energy and food prices has eroded disposable incomes, and war-related uncertainty has contributed to lower investment.

To become energy independent, Moldovan wineries, as well as the state, need to strive to utilize alternative energy sources. Already today, Moldovan wineries can be found that almost completely cover their energy needs from alternative sources (installing solar panels, initially designing buildings with energy efficiency in mind). Government support in the form of incentives for sustainable practices and quality certification, as well as international cooperation and trade agreements, contributes to the sustainable development of the winemaking industry. Creating a strong brand

identity is crucial for Moldovan wines to stand out in the global market. Highlighting the unique characteristics of Moldovan wines, such as local grape varieties and traditional winemaking methods, can attract discerning consumers. Effective marketing strategies, including participation in international wine fairs and competitions, can enhance visibility and reputation.

Ensuring economic sustainability also involves supporting small and medium-sized winemakers, who are an integral part of the industry. These producers often face challenges related to scale, market access, and financial resources.

The sustainability of Moldovan winemaking requires a comprehensive approach that considers environmental, economic, and social aspects. Through innovation, adaptation to global trends, and international cooperation, Moldova can ensure a sustainable future for its winemaking industry, benefiting the economy, the environment, and society as a whole.

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